

Ionic Diels-Alder Reaction : Recent Developments[†]

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Diels-Alder reaction¹ is one of the most important reactions in organic chemistry permitting C-C bond formations with high degree of predictable regio-, stereo- and enantioselectivities in most of the cases. Enormous amount of data is available in the literature where applications of the original Diels-Alder reaction as well as its numerous modifications in organic synthesis have been studied². The mechanistic details of these cycloadditions have been discussed and widely debated³. Both concerted synchronous as well as asynchronous pathways for different Diels-Alder reactions have been suggested. In a few cases, completely stepwise 'formal' (4+2)cycloaddition processes have been suggested⁴. At the same time, some Diels-Alder type reactions catalysed by protic acids, have been reported⁵ scantily. It is mainly through the recent efforts by Gassman and coworkers that such Diels-Alder reactions have become popular. In this review recent developments of this interesting class of reaction have been outlined including some work from the authors laboratory at IIT Kanpur also.

Intrigued by the possibility of applying cationic cyclisation and the cation radical catalysed Diels-Alder reaction⁵ to the intramolecular (4+2)cycloaddition of unactivated polyene systems, Gassman and Singleton⁶ in 1984 demonstrated the intramolecular cyclisations of tetraenes (1 → 2 and 2a) (Scheme 1) via protic acid or aminium cation radical catalysts in high yield with excellent stereospecificity. The aminium cation radical in some systems appears to act mainly as an indirect source of protons, which are then utilised in an acid-catalysed cyclisation.

Scheme 1

In order to test whether the addition of aminium cation radical to the reaction mixture was merely leading to the generation of a protic acid which was the true catalytic species, and also to extend their work to intermolecular

(4+2)cycloaddition, Gassman and Singleton⁷ examined the dimerisation of 2,4-dimethyl-1,3-pentadiene 3 (Scheme 2) as catalysed by tris(*p*-bromophenyl)aminium hexachloroantimonate. They found that cation radical promoted Diels-Alder reactions can be readily distinguished from the corresponding protic acid catalysed processes, and the dimerisation of 3 is a protic acid catalysed reaction. The true cation radical dimerisation of 3 is a relatively slow process leading to the formation of entirely different dimer 5.

Scheme 2

Later in 1986⁸, the same authors used allylic alcohols and allylic ethers as precursors of specific allyl cations in an intramolecular ionic Diels-Alder reaction in order to gain complete control of the regiochemistry of the cycloaddition. Thus, for example, they indicated the potential of ionic Diels-Alder reactions in the synthesis of diverse polycyclic molecules and exemplified it by the intramolecular cyclisation of 6 into 2 (Scheme 3) using triflic acid as a catalyst. Likewise, 7 was found to give 8 under acidic conditions. Obviously, the presence of OH and OMe groups at appropriate positions lead to defined carbocations for the intramolecular cycloadditions to begin. This leads to high regioselectivity, stereospecificity and good yield in these reactions. No hydroxylic products resulting from the capture of water by the intermediate cations were observed. This confirmed the viability of using allylic alcohols as allyl cation precursors in the intramolecular ionic Diels-Alder reaction.

It is well known that the activity of a dienophile in the Diels-Alder reaction increases with the electron-withdrawing power of the substituent group and since a carbocation is one of the strongest electron-withdrawing substituents known, the extreme reactivity of allyl cations, as described above, in the Diels-Alder reaction is not surprising. In continuation of their studies, Gassman and Singleton^{9a} reported that the triple bond of the 1,1-diphenylpropargyl cation 9 is a powerful dienophile which adds to 1,3-diene in high yield

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Scheme 3

at ambient temperatures to give the corresponding cycloadducts **10** (Scheme 4). Although there is a report^{9b} in the literature which shows poor yield of a propargyl cation in the Diels-Alder reactions but now it has been proved beyond doubt that an acetylene adjacent to a carbocation is a powerful dienophile.

tetraene system, e.g. **13** through a judicious choice of methyl substitution, acid catalyst and temperature. This scheme turned out to be particularly useful in the synthesis of bicyclo[5.4.0]undecanes which are not readily prepared.

Mechanistically¹¹, a stepwise process has been postulated for these ionic Diels-Alder reactions by Gorman and

Scheme 4

Gassman and Gorman¹⁰ further demonstrated that the potential of ionic Diels-Alder reaction can be diversified by controlling the ring size. For this purpose, through careful manipulation of the methyl substitution pattern on the tetraene, the authors determined the site of protonation and the regioselectivity of the addition of the allyl cation to the 1,3-diene. Treatment of 2-methyl-1,3,8,10-undecatetraene **11** with $\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ was studied which gave **12** in 86% yield (Scheme 5). In contrast, **13** gave products **14-16** which were consistent with the protonation of **13** on C_d to produce tetrasubstituted allyl cation. They found that the bicyclo[4.4.0]decyl,¹⁴ or bicyclo[5.4.0]undecyl^{15,16} ring systems can be produced from substituted 1,3,8,10-undeca-

Gassman¹². They synthesised several tetraenes, comprising primarily of methylated analogs of (3*E*,8*E*)-1,3,8,10-undecatetraene **17**, and treated them with acid to study the influence of alkyl substitution on the intramolecular Diels-Alder reaction. Depending on the methyl substitution pattern of these tetraenes, bicyclo[4.3.0]nonyl, bicyclo[4.4.0]decyl and bicyclo[5.4.0]undecyl ring systems were produced. The irreversible and stereoselective formation of the same Diels-Alder product from two non-interconverting tetraenes **17** and **18**, which differed only by the *cis-trans* relationship of a terminal methyl group, was best explained by a stepwise process (Scheme 6). The allyl cation can either cyclise directly or deprotonate to produce different products. This also

Scheme 5

Scheme 6

suggests that protonation-deprotonation reactions are reversible in most of the cases while cyclisation reactions are not reversible.

Gassman and coworkers also explored¹³ acrolein acetals as allyl cation precursors in their pursuit of ionic Diels-Alder reaction. This was particularly studied because the Diels-Alder reactions that employ acrolein as a dienophile often give undesirable results due to the ease of polymerisation of acrolein. In order to circumvent this problem, a variety of Lewis acids¹⁴ and high pressures¹⁵ have been employed by some chemists. Even under these conditions, yields are often less than 50%. The experience of Gassman and coworkers in the field of ionic Diels-Alder reaction (*vide supra*) led them¹³ to tackle the above mentioned problem of the polymerisation of acrolein. They considered employing allyl cations of the type **22** (Scheme 7), obtainable from acrolein **21** upon acid treatment, for Diels-Alder reaction which gave poor to fair yields of the cycloadducts **24**.

Scheme 7

Gassman *et al.*¹³ reasoned that the possible cause for the mediocre yields of these cycloadducts was the diffusion of the alcohol away from the cation **23** with resultant failure to recombine to yield **24**. They, however, circumvented this problem by choosing 2-vinyl-1,3-dioxolane **25** as the precursor of allyl cations of the type **26** (Scheme 8). In this case it was expected that the cation formed after the cycloaddition would have the alcohol moiety tethered and held in the proximity (*cf.* **27**) of the resulting carbocation. By doing so, they found a dramatic increase in the yield of

the cycloadduct **28** and this marked the beginning of the useful ionic Diels-Alder reaction using olefinic acetals.

Scheme 8

Exploring a variety of applications of this principle to other systems, Gassman and Chavan¹⁶ developed a method for the formal low-temperature addition of triethyl orthopropiolate **29** (Scheme 9) to 1,3-dienes in the presence of trimethylsilyl triflate via the intermediacy of the propargyl cation **30**. Extending the concept, they then reported¹⁷ that triethyl orthoacrylate **33** (Scheme 9) served as an excellent precursor of the 1,1-diethoxyallyl cation **34** which added to 1,3-dienes, such as cyclohexa-1,3-diene at low temperatures, to produce, as the final products, the corresponding adducts of ethyl acrylate.

From this study it became clear that 1,1-diethoxyallyl cation **34** is an extremely powerful dienophile in comparison to ethyl acrylate, even when the ethyl acrylate was used in the presence of triflic acid. This low temperature process offers a unique method for the synthesis of these adducts under very mild conditions. As expected, the fate of the in-

Scheme 9

intermediate diethoxy substituted cation suggested that **32** gives ethyl ester and not the corresponding *ortho*-ester. In an attempt to design a dienophile in which the carboxylic acid would remain protected as an *ortho*-ester, 1-vinyl-4-methyl-2,6,7-trioxabicyclo[2.2.2]octane **35** (Scheme 10) was added by Gassman and Chavan¹⁸ to 1,3-dienes under catalysis by boron trifluoride-diethyl ether to provide synthetically useful yields of Diels-Alder adduct **36** having an *ortho*-ester as the major functional group, which could be readily converted into the corresponding carboxylic acid **37**.

Scheme 10

Gassman *et al.*¹⁹ established a stepwise process in the ionic Diels-Alder reaction by giving further evidences in this direction. Earlier they²⁰ had found that a decrease in the ring size of the (1*Z*,3*E*)-cycloalkadiene **38**, required a compensating increase in the reactivity of the dienophile **39**, in order to obtain acceptable yields of **40**. For ring sizes $n = 7$ and 8 , maleic anhydride, dicyanoacetylene, and hexafluoro-2-butyne were found to be useful dienophiles. However for $n = 5$ and 6 , the more reactive dienophile, *N*-phenyl-1,2,4-triazoline-3,5-dione, was required in order to

Scheme 11

obtain acceptable yields of the desired inside-outside bicyclic compounds^{20b}. In view of the finding that allyl cations are among the most powerful dienophiles in existence, Gassman *et al.*¹⁹ added allyl cation to cyclic dienes in the hope to produce highly strained bicyclic adducts. When an

allyl cation derived from protonation of 2-vinyl-1,3-dioxolane **41** was added to dienes **42** and **43**, (2+2)cycloadducts **44** and **45** (Scheme 11), rather than the corresponding (4+2)cycloadducts, were obtained.

The stereochemistry at the ring junction clearly suggested that (2+2)cycloaddition is a stepwise process and a plausible pathway is shown in Scheme 12.

As a consequence of these observations that (2+2)- and not (4+2)cycloaddition occurs under certain conditions, Gassman and Lottes²¹ studied systematically such cycloadditions by taking a variety of unactivated olefins and olefinic acetals. A variety of carbocation activated olefins have been shown to add to unactivated olefins in a (2+2)cycloaddition to yield cyclobutanes (Scheme 13)²¹. In this study, it was further observed that allyl cations, derived from olefinic acetals, add intermolecularly to those olefins which yield tertiary carbocations. It is clear that such reactions can occur through a stepwise process only. Further, these results substantiate the mechanism proposed for the formation of the second carbon-carbon bond in the stepwise (4+2)cycloaddition of allyl cations to 1,3-dienes also.

Hashimoto *et al.*²² reported a unique application of 2,2-dimethoxyethyl acrylate **46** as dienophiles in ionic Diels-Alder reaction, akin to the ones originally described by Gassman, in the presence of Lewis acid such as titanium(IV) chloride. The authors claim their method to be superior in the points of the availability of the starting materials and

Scheme 12

high diastereo- and regioselectivity. Here a cationic species **47** is responsible for cycloaddition to occur. They have further observed²³ that in the presence of trimethylsilyl trifluoromethane sulfonate (TMSOTf) and methoxytrimethylsilane (MeOTMS) the species such as **49** could be

Scheme 13

generated from 2-oxopropyl acrylate **48** which also undergoes Diels-Alder reaction with a variety of dienes (Scheme 14).

Scheme 14

Application of this method using cyclic oxocarbenium ion **50** (Scheme 15) in carrying out asymmetric ionic Diels-Alder reaction has been recently reported by Sammakia and Berliner²⁴. The potential advantage of this method lies in the fact that the protecting group for the hydroxyl serves as the activating group and that cyclic vinyl oxocarbenium ions larger than five-membered rings would be accessible, affording opportunities for remote asymmetric induction in Diels-Alder reaction.

Scheme 15

Attempts to make use of chiral acetal derived dienophiles such as **51** (Scheme 16) in asymmetric ionic Diels-Alder reaction have been reported by Alexakis and Mangeney²⁵. Although the chemical yields of the cycloadducts were high, the diastereoselectivity was rather low (13%). However, re-

cently, Sammakia and Berliner²⁶ have reported that similar types of chiral dienophiles derived from 2,4-pentanediol undergo Lewis acid, instead of protic acid, promoted Diels-Alder reaction with good diastereoselectivity (78%). The reaction most likely occurs via an acyclic oxo-carbenium ion intermediate. Hydrolysis of the cycloadducts eventually leads to optically pure cyclohexene carboxaldehyde derivatives **52** (Scheme 16).

Tartaric acid derived chiral diols possessing C-2 symmetry have been employed²⁷ as chiral acetal and a fair degree of success in terms of very high diastereoselectivity in many reactions have been achieved. Our own experience²⁸ in the use of chiral acetals in asymmetric synthesis as well

as that of others have led us to believe that side-chain appendages bearing oxygen atoms such as COOEt , CH_2OMe

Scheme 16

Scheme 17

Scheme 18

and CH₂OCH₂Ph are better than methyl groups. This is because the former ones provide extra chelation through oxygen atoms in reactions where Lewis acids are used. Towards this effect dienophiles derived from crotonaldehyde were utilised for ionic Diels-Alder reactions²⁹. Out of the three dienophiles, viz. **53**, **54**, **55** used, **53** appeared to be the best and among the Lewis acids used, viz. BF₃.Et₂O, TiCl₄ and TiCl₂(iPrO)₂, the last one was the acid of choice. For example, cyclopentadiene reacted with **53** to give the cycloadduct **56** in 76% yield with 78% d/e of the *endo*-product. The *endo/exo* ratio was 74 : 26. Likewise, isoprene reacted with **53** to give the cycloadduct **57** in 72% yield and 76% d/e (Scheme 17).

Recently Grieco *et al.*³⁰ have found that LiClO₄.Et₂O (4M solution) in the presence of 1% camphorsulfonic acid permits ionic Diels-Alder reaction of olefinic acetals derived from cyclic as well as acyclic enones. This is particularly important for cyclohexenone acetals and their derivatives since the parent enones are notoriously known³¹ to be reluctant to undergo Diels-Alder reaction even at high temperatures or under Lewis acid catalysis. In contrast, the LiClO₄.Et₂O/1% camphorsulfonic acid catalyst system allows these reactions to proceed at room temperature and in excellent yields. A few representative examples are shown in Scheme 18. We have, on the other hand, found²⁹ that LiClO₄.MeNO₂ solution (4M) does not require the addition of 1% camphorsulfonic acid. An apparent reason appears in the increase in dipole moment going from Et₂O to MeNO₂. Further, we have also found that Nafion-H³², a resin sulfonic acid, is an excellent acid catalyst for such ionic Diels-Alder reactions. An obvious advantage is the ease of workup which requires mere filtration.

In summary, ionic Diels-Alder reactions as described in this review lead to a variety of cyclic adducts under mild

conditions. Both (4+2)- as well as (2+2)cycloadditions could be readily carried out with acid catalysts. Variations both in terms of structures of the dienophilic component as well as catalysts have been studied. The potential of these reactions has not been fully explored and future should witness developments in asymmetric variation, improvements in accommodating varied substrates and application in the synthesis of natural products.

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